

The Role of Appearance Customization in Children's Interactions with Conversational Agents

Jasmine E. Tran

University of California, Irvine
jasetran@uci.edu

ABSTRACT

The proposed research examines how visual customization influences children's engagement with conversational agents (CAs) and its influence on STEM identity. Using a mixed-methods approach, children interact with one of three CA conditions: text-based, randomized avatar, or customizable avatar. By utilizing clickstream data, audiovisual recordings, and child interviews, I aim to explore children's interaction patterns, design choices, and perceptions of CAs. Findings will inform the development of inclusive, user-centered educational technologies, enhancing engagement and personalization in AI-driven learning tools.

KEYWORDS

Conversational agents, avatar-based customization, personalization, STEM identity

INTRODUCTION

Conversational agents (CAs) have gained widespread recognition, particularly through their integration into smart speakers like Siri, Alexa, and Google Home. Beyond their use in household applications, CAs are being increasingly explored as tools to enhance learning experiences for diverse students. Personalized CAs in education research have strong potential to bridge resource gaps and provide individualized learning experiences, moving away from the traditional one-size-fits-all approach. Personalization in CAs is broadly defined, ranging from simply addressing users by name to responding based on past user-provided information. Some studies suggest that AI-driven personalization, which collects and analyzes large amounts of user data to adapt tailored learning experiences, encourages deeper engagement and comprehension (Das et al., 2023). Conversely, research on personalization that relies solely on the explicit reuse of prior user-provided information has found no significant impact on user behavior (Araujo & Bol, 2024).

While extensive research exists on the effects of personalized CAs, most of these studies focused on disembodied CAs, or text or speech-based agents that lack a physical form, amongst samples of higher education students (Yusuf et al., 2025). Further research with children is critical because children are increasingly exposed to technology and AI educational tools, and they have diverse learning preferences and abilities across textual, auditory, and visual modalities. Given the importance of visualization in early cognitive development—particularly for young learners who may still be developing reading and auditory comprehension skills—the present work focuses on embodied CAs that have “some degree of visual or humanistic form” (Yusuf et al., 2025). This knowledge can inform the visual design of interactive CAs, and potentially foster STEM identity among marginalized children by providing them with the agency to create their own agents.

PROPOSED RESEARCH

While Xu et al. (2024) showed that verbal engagement with CAs increased science learning, their study used fixed PBS KIDS characters which limited children's control over the agent's appearance. Thus, I will use an experimental design in which children will interact with one of three types of CAs: (1) text-based, (2) randomized (pre-assigned avatar), or (3) customizable (personalized avatar). This study examines differences in children's interaction patterns and engagement rates across these conditions. The following research questions guide this investigation:

RQ1: How do children engage with disembodied versus embodied CAs? Does customization influence children's interactions with and perceptions of embodied CAs?

RQ2: What factors shape the design choices children make when customizing their CA? What thoughts do children have about their conversational partner in relation to their own STEM identity?

Related Literature

Avatar-based Customization

One approach to personalization explored in learning games research is avatar-based customization, which allows users to create or modify avatars according to their preferences. Studies have shown that users who customize their avatars feel a stronger connection to them (Turkay & Kinzer, 2016) and experience greater engagement and immersion in learning environments (Che et al., 2018). Integrating this concept with conversational agents (CAs) could similarly enhance children's engagement by strengthening their sense of identification and fostering parasocial relationships with the agent. Customization choices may also reveal what children value in their conversational

partners, whether they prefer fantastical avatars or ones that reflect their real-world identity, providing valuable insights for researchers, educators, and developers to create more effective and engaging educational tools.

STEM Identity

Customization offers important benefits concerning representation in character design, which is often shaped by masculine, heteronormative and formulaic tropes (Tompkins & Martin, 2021). This lack of diversity is concerning, as representation plays a critical role in fostering STEM identity—defined as being recognized by oneself and others as a STEM person, grounded in belonging, confidence, and competence (Carlone & Johnson, 2007). Because media and educational tools influence children's academic aspirations, marginalized children who rarely see themselves represented may internalize exclusionary stereotypes. Role models who mirror their identities can act as a "social vaccine," fostering belonging and challenging these stereotypes (Dasgupta, 2011). Allowing children to design CAs that reflect their unique cultures, gender identities, or valued figures like parents or teachers could enhance engagement and strengthen STEM identity, helping children connect their personal identities to STEM success.

METHODOLOGY

To address prior challenges in CA research related to limited triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data (Khosrawi-Rad et al., 2022), this study will use a mixed-methods approach. Children will interact with a web application integrated with OpenAI's API and will be randomly assigned to one of three CAs. The text-based CA functions like a chatbot, displaying text responses as the child verbally interacts. In contrast, the randomized and customized CAs will feature visual avatars with varying expressions. Children in the customized condition will be able to personalize their CA using the provided options in the app before beginning their conversation with the CA (**Figure 1**). All CAs will also respond verbally in addition to visual aspects to support younger children who may still have difficulty with reading. The conversational flow of the AI agent will follow the structure outlined in Xu et al. (2024), incorporating scaffolding to support children of all ability levels.

Children will then engage in a conversation with their assigned CA focused on computational thinking and sequential direction-following. Parents, guardians, or teachers may be present to assist with technology, but they will be instructed to allow the child to interact with the CA independently to avoid influencing the child's engagement patterns and responses. For comparing engagement rate and patterns between groups, the app will automatically collect clickstream data and audio-visual recordings of children's interactions with the CA. Additionally, semi-structured Zoom interviews will be conducted to explore children's perceptions of their CA, their interaction experiences, and their views on STEM learning. Children in the customized CA group will also be asked about their design choices and creative process. These interviews will provide rich data on how children's experiences and engagement varied based on the type of CA they interacted with. Both the interaction session and the child interview will each take approximately 45 to 60 minutes, totaling about 2 hours for the full study.

Participants and Site

Participants

Forty-five children (15 per condition), aged 4 to 12, will be recruited through purposeful sampling to ensure a diverse sample of ethnic groups (Maxwell, 2012). Given this study's focus on children's identities and connection to their CA's appearance, purposeful sampling ensures a broader range of perspectives and helps address the overrepresentation of WEIRD (Western, educated, industrialized, rich, and democratic) populations in research (Nielsen et al., 2017).

Site

This study will be conducted entirely online, eliminating the need for a physical data collection site and reflecting real-life practices in which children engage with technology across various settings. Participants and researchers will be able to access the web app through a simple link, and child interviews will also be held over Zoom.

LIMITATIONS

The relatively small sample size in this study limits broad generalizations and comparisons across different backgrounds or STEM identities. However, this is mitigated by in-depth qualitative analysis, which leverages audio-visual recordings and child interviews to capture real-time interactions with CAs—an approach that would be challenging with a larger sample. The broader impact of this research also depends on whether visually customizable CAs can enhance children's learning. While this is a crucial question, assessing learning outcomes requires significant resources. Future advancements in AI and increased resources could expand this research, but the current study provides a strong foundation for exploring the role of customization in educational technology.

CONCLUSION

In summary, as CAs and AI become increasingly prevalent in education, it is crucial to understand how children interact with these technologies and the factors that influence these interactions. Incorporating visual elements and providing children with the power to personalize educational CAs or AI-integrated tools is an effective way to make

learning more fun and engaging. Instead of viewing personalization of the CA as solely a decision made by researchers, educators, or developers, the design of these tools can involve the users themselves. To explore this process, I designed a custom-made app integrated with three different forms of CAs. This research bridges gaps between quantitative and qualitative CA research through credible analyses of surveys, audio-video recordings, clickstream data, and semi-structured interviews. Thus, this research will greatly contribute to lingering design and personalization questions within the education technology field. Ultimately, this study has significant implications for more user-centered design in educational technologies, empowering children to shape their learning experiences and create more effective, personalized AI-based tools.

TABLES & FIGURES

Figure 1. Conversational agent (CA) customization screen in web application

GENERATIVE AI USE

I employed generative AI, specifically ChatGPT, to revise writing that was initially drafted by myself. In addition, ChatGPT was used to format citations and references into APA-7 format. I evaluated the output by carefully checking said output to ensure quality writing. The author assumes all responsibility for the content of this submission.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you to Young-Jin Park as this work would not have been possible without his guidance in app development and design!

REFERENCES

- Araujo, T. & Bol, N. (2024). From speaking like a person to being personal: The effects of personalized, regular interactions with conversational agents. *Computers in Human Behaviors: Artificial Humans*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbah.2023.100030>.
- Calvert, S.L., & Richards, M.N. (2014). Children's parasocial relationships. In A. B. Jordan & D. Romer (Eds.), *Media and the well-being of children and adolescents* (pp. 187–200). Oxford University Press.
- Carlone, H.B. & Johnson, A. (2007). Understanding the science experiences of successful women of color: Science identity as an analytic lens. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 44(8), 1187-1218. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.20237>
- Chen, Z. H., Lu, H. D., & Lu, C. H. (2018). The effects of human factors on the use of avatars in game-based learning: Customization vs. non-customization. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 35(4–5), 384–394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2018.1543090>.
- Das, A., Malaviya, S., Singh, M. (2023). The impact of AI-driven personalization on learners' performance. *International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering*, 11(8), 15-22. <http://doi.org/10.26438/ijcse/v11i8.1522>.

- Dasgupta, N. (2011). Ingroup Experts and Peers as Social Vaccines Who Inoculate the Self-Concept: The Stereotype Inoculation Model. *Psychological Inquiry*, 22(4), 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1047840X.2011.607313>.
- Fawcett, C. A., & Markson, L. (2010). Children reason about shared preferences. *Developmental Psychology*, 46(2), 299–309. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0018539>.
- Khosrawi-Rad, B., Rinn, H., Schlimbach, R., Gebbing, P., Yang, X., Lattemann, C., Markgraf, D., & Robra-Bissantz, S. (2022). Conversational Agents in Education – A Systematic Literature Review. *The European Conference on Information Systems 2022 Proceedings*, ECIS.
- Lauricella, A. R., Gola, A. A. H., & Calvert, S. L. (2011). Toddlers' Learning From Socially Meaningful Video Characters. *Media Psychology*, 14(2), 216–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15213269.2011.573465>
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach*. Sage publications.
- Nielsen, M., Haun, D., Kärtner, J., & Legare, C. H. (2017). The persistent sampling bias in developmental psychology: A call to action. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 162, 31–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2017.04.017>.
- Tompkins, J. E., & Martins, N. (2021). Masculine Pleasures as Normalized Practices: Character Design in the Video Game Industry. *Games and Culture*, 17(3), 399-420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15554120211034760>
- Turkay, S. & Kinzer, C. K. (2016). The effects of avatar-based customization on player identification. *International Journal of Gaming and Computer-Mediated Simulations*, 6(1), 1-25. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4018/ijgcms.2014010101>
- Xu, Y., He, K., Levine, J., Ritchie, D., Pan, Z., Bustamante, A., & Warschauer, M. (2024). Artificial intelligence enhances children's science learning from television shows. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 116(7), 1071–1092. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000889>.
- Yusuf, H., Money, A. & Daylamani-Zad, D. (2025). Pedagogical AI conversational agents in higher education: a conceptual framework and survey of the state of the art. *Education Technology Research and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-025-10447-4>